

Pickelhaube – Tee-Pee ECG Double Whammy!

Taylor Goulding-Avedisian, M.D.^a, Deeksha Acharya, M.D.^a, Abdul Moiz Qureshi, M.D.^a,
Bassam Omar, M.D., Ph.D.^{a, b}, Suganya Manoharan, M.D.^a, Christopher Malozzi, D.O.^a

Description

A young patient admitted with multiple abdominal and chest gunshot wounds is in shock with multiple electrolyte abnormalities. Initial electrocardiogram (ECG) revealed a dome-and-spike pattern in the inferior leads (Fig. A) resembling a Prussian spiked helmet (Pickelhaube), reflective of severe systemic illness, shock, elevated lactate level and abdomino-thoracic injuries. The anterior leads revealed peaking of the T waves indicative of hyperkalemia in addition to prominent U waves reflective of initial low ionized calcium and low magnesium, giving the appearance of a teepee. Multiple surgeries in addition to electrolyte adjustment resulted in stabilization and resolution of the acute ECG findings (Fig. B).

Discussion

The spiked helmet (Pickelhaube) sign on ECG appears as ST elevations before and after the QRS complex (Dome and spike pattern) which can mimic myocardial injury. However, it is not a sign of cardiac pathology [1]. Its mechanism remains poorly understood, but it has been suggested to be due to pulsatile contractions of the diaphragm versus local mechanical or electrical interference with electrodes.

In one case report review [2] 59% of patients with this sign died, particularly within 24 hours of diagnosis. Anterior lead involvement was associated with worst prognosis, followed by lateral and then inferior lead involvement. Inferior lead spiked helmet sign had a higher association with intra-abdominal pathology.

The Tee-Pee sign on ECG manifests as a peaked T where the descending limb of the T wave prolongs and fuses with the p wave mimicking a teepee [3]. It is a sign of multiple electrolyte abnormalities with hyperkalemia causing the peaking of the T wave while hypomagnesemia and hypocalcemia causing the appearance of a prominent U wave responsible for the prolonged descending limb of the T wave [4].

Manuscript submitted Aug 25, accepted Aug 28, 2025
a Division of Cardiology, University of South Alabama,
Mobile, AL 36617

b Corresponding Author: Bassam Omar, Division of
Cardiology, University of South Alabama, 2451 USA
Medical Center Dr., Mobile, AL 36617, USA.

Email: bomar@health.southalabama.edu

<https://cardiofellows.com/newsletter-august-2025.html>

References

1. Hamade H, Jabri A, Yusaf A, et al. The Spiked Helmet Sign: A Concerning Electrocardiographic Finding. *JACC Case Rep.* 2021 Sep 1;3(11):1370-1372.
2. Mahmoudi E, Hui JMH, Leung KSK, et al. Spiked Helmet Electrocardiographic Sign-A Systematic Review of Case Reports. *Curr Probl Cardiol.* 2023 Mar;48(3):101535.
3. Johri AM, Baranchuk A, Simpson CS, et al. ECG manifestations of multiple electrolyte imbalance: peaked T wave to P wave ("tee-pee sign"). *Ann Noninvasive Electrocardiol.* 2009 Apr;14(2):211-4.
4. Elsayed YMH (2020). Hypocalcemia-induced Camel-hump T-wave, Tee-Pee sign, and bradycardia in a car-painter of a complexed dilemma: A case report. *Cardiac* 2(1):07.

KEYWORDS: Spiked Helmet Sign; Pickelhaube Sign, Tee-Pee Sign; Electrocardiogram.

Reference this article as:

Goulding-Avedisian T, Acharya D, Qureshi AM, Omar B, Manoharan S, Malozzi C. Pickelhaube – Tee-Pee ECG Double Whammy! *Cardiofel Newslet* 2025. August; 8(8):16 – 17.